

HIGHER-ORDER THEORETICAL MOMENTS FOR RANDOM VARIABLES AND THEIR INTERRELATIONSHIPS

M.J. Namazov

**Jizzakh State Pedagogical University
named after A. Qodiriy**

Abstract: This article discusses random variables and their numerical characteristics, as well as the interrelation within the theory of moments. In addition, both central and raw moments are individually described for each random variable.

Keywords: Mathematical expectation, variance, moment theory, raw moment, central moment, moments for single-variable functions.

The issues of mean value and dispersion for random variables are thoroughly covered within the topics of mathematical expectation and variance. The relationship between the variance of a linear function of a random variable and the expected value of that linear function is also discussed. There are relationships between the variance of a linear function of a random variable and the calculation of the mathematical expectation of that linear function, namely:

$$D(X) = M[X - M(X)]^2 = M(X^2) - M^2(X) \quad (1)$$

If the random variable is discrete:

$$D(X) = \sum_{i=1} x_i^2 \cdot p_i - \left(\sum_{i=1} x_i \cdot p_i \right)^2 \quad (2)$$

If the random variable is continuous:

$$D(X) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} x^2 \cdot f(x) dx - \left(\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} x \cdot f(x) dx \right)^2 \quad (3)$$

The above studies indicate that if random variables are not linear, calculating their numerical characteristics becomes difficult. In this context, this article discusses the nature of nonlinear (polynomial) random variables.

Let us consider a discrete random variable X given by the distribution law of the following single-digit prime numbers:

X	2	3	5	7
P	0,5	0,3	0,18	0,02

Let us find the mathematical expectation of X :

$$M(X) = 2 \cdot 0,5 + 3 \cdot 0,3 + 5 \cdot 0,18 + 7 \cdot 0,02 = 2,94$$

Let us find the distribution law of X^2 :

X^2	4	9	25	49
P	0,5	0,3	0,18	0,02

Let us calculate the mathematical expectation of X^2

$$M(X^2) = 4 \cdot 0,5 + 9 \cdot 0,3 + 25 \cdot 0,18 + 49 \cdot 0,02 = 10,18.$$

We can see that the value of $M(X^2)$ is significantly greater than $M(X)$. This is due to the fact that the value of $X=7$, when squared, becomes 49 — a substantial increase — while its probability is small (0.02).

Therefore, transitioning from $M(X)$ to $M(X^2)$ allows us to better account for the influence of large values with small probabilities on the expected value. Naturally, if the random variable X has several large values with small probabilities, then calculating X^2 , and especially X^3 , X^4 , and so on, increases the “role” of these rare but large values. For this reason, it is appropriate to investigate the mathematical expectations of all positive integer powers of the random variable.

The k -th order raw moment of a random variable X is defined as the mathematical expectation of X^k :

$$\nu_k = M(X^k) \quad (4)$$

$$\begin{cases} v_1 = M(X) \\ v_2 = M(X^2) \\ \dots \\ v_n = M(X^n) \end{cases}$$

In particular, for both discrete and continuous random variables XXX, the first-order raw moment is equal to the mathematical expectation:

$$v_1 = M(X) = \sum_{i=1} x_i \cdot p_i = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} x \cdot f(x) dx \quad (5)$$

For discrete and continuous random variables XXX, the first-order raw moment is given as follows:

$$v_2 = M(X^2) = \sum_{i=1} x_i^2 \cdot p_i = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} x^2 \cdot f(x) dx \quad (6)$$

The k-th order central moment of a random variable X is defined as the mathematical expectation of $(X - M(X))^k$, i.e., the k-th power of the deviation from the mean. $\mu_k = M[X - M(X)]^k$ (7)

$$\begin{aligned} \mu_1 &= 0 \\ \mu_2 &= M[X - M(X)]^2 = D(X) \\ &\dots \\ \mu_n &= M[X - M(X)]^n \end{aligned}$$

In particular, for both discrete and continuous random variables XXX, the first-order central moment is equal to zero:

$$\mu_1 = M[X - M(X)]^1 = M(X) - M(X) = 0$$

The second-order central moment is equal to the variance:

$$\begin{aligned} \mu_2 &= M[X - M(X)]^2 = D(X) = \\ &= \sum_{i=1} x_i^2 \cdot p_i - \left(\sum_{i=1} x_i \cdot p_i \right)^2 = \\ D(X) &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} x^2 \cdot f(x) dx - \left(\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} x \cdot f(x) dx \right)^2 \quad (8) \end{aligned}$$

Based on the given data and the Newton binomial formula provided below, we establish the relationship between one moment and another.

Binomial formula:

$$(a - b)^n = \sum_{k=0}^n C_n^k \cdot a^{n-k} \cdot b^k \quad (\text{Bu yerda } n \geq k) \quad (9)$$

If n is even: $(a - b)^n = C_n^0 \cdot a^n \cdot b^0 - C_n^1 \cdot a^{n-1} \cdot b^1 + \dots + C_n^n \cdot a^0 \cdot b^n = a^n - n \cdot a^{n-1} \cdot b^1 + \dots + b^n$ (10)

If n is odd: $(a - b)^n = C_n^0 \cdot a^n \cdot b^0 - C_n^1 \cdot a^{n-1} \cdot b^1 + \dots - C_n^n \cdot a^0 \cdot b^n = a^n - n \cdot a^{n-1} \cdot b^1 + \dots - b^n$ (11)

Using the formula given above (4) and the properties of mathematical expectation, we derive the raw moments up to order n:

$$v_1 = M(X) = \sum_{i=1}^k x_i^1 \cdot p_i$$

$$v_2 = M(X^2) = \sum_{i=1}^k x_i^2 \cdot p_i$$

.....

$$v_n = M(X^n) = \sum_{i=1}^k x_i^n \cdot p_i$$

$$\mu_n = M[X - M(X)]^n = M[(X - M(X))^n] = \sum_{i=1}^k (x_i - M(X))^n \cdot p_i$$

From the above expression, we return again to the Newton binomial:

$$(x_i - M(X))^n = \sum_{k=0}^n (-1)^k \cdot C_n^k \cdot x_i^{n-k} \cdot M(X)^k$$

If $(x_i - M(X))^n$, where n is an even number, then according to equality (10) :

$$C_n^0 \cdot x_i^n \cdot M(X)^0 - C_n^1 \cdot x_i^{n-1} \cdot M(X)^1 + \dots - C_n^{n-1} \cdot x_i^1 \cdot M(X)^{n-1} + C_n^n \cdot x_i^0 \cdot M(X)^n =$$

$$= x_i^n - n \cdot x_i^{n-1} \cdot M(X)^1 + \dots - n \cdot x_i \cdot M(X)^{n-1} + M(X)^n$$

If $(x_i - M(X))^n$, where n is an odd number, then according to equality (11):

$$C_n^0 \cdot x_i^n \cdot M(X)^0 - C_n^1 \cdot x_i^{n-1} \cdot M(X)^1 + \dots + C_n^{n-1} \cdot x_i^1 \cdot M(X)^{n-1} - C_n^n \cdot x_i^0 \cdot M(X)^n =$$

$$= x_i^n - n \cdot x_i^{n-1} \cdot M(X)^1 + \dots + n \cdot x_i \cdot M(X)^{n-1} - M(X)^n$$

Substituting the resulting expressions into (12), we obtain the following:

$$\mu_n = \sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - M(X))^n \cdot p_i = (x_i^n - n \cdot x_i^{n-1} \cdot M(X)^1 + \dots - n \cdot x_i \cdot M(X)^{n-1} + M(X)^n) \cdot p_i \text{ yoki}$$

$$\mu_n = \sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - M(X))^n \cdot p_i = (x_i^n - n \cdot x_i^{n-1} \cdot M(X)^1 + \dots + n \cdot x_i \cdot M(X)^{n-1} - M(X)^n) \cdot p_i$$

We can write it in the form $(M(X)^{n-1} - M(X)^n) \cdot p_i$. After that, we multiply each term by p_i , corresponding to even and odd values of n.

If n is even: $\mu_n = x_i^n \cdot p_i - n \cdot x_i^{n-1} \cdot p_i \cdot M(X)^1 + \dots - n \cdot x_i \cdot p_i \cdot M(X)^{n-1} + M(X)^n \cdot p_i$

If p_i or n is odd: $\mu_n = x_i^n \cdot p_i - n \cdot x_i^{n-1} \cdot p_i \cdot M(X)^1 + \dots + n \cdot x_i \cdot p_i \cdot M(X)^{n-1} - M(X)^n \cdot p_i$. we write it in the form shown above.

We obtain $\mu_n = M(X^n) - n \cdot M(X^{n-1}) \cdot M(X)^1 + \dots - n \cdot M(X) \cdot M(X)^{n-1} + M(X)^n \cdot M(X^0)$ or $\mu_n = M(X^n) - n \cdot M(X^{n-1}) \cdot M(X)^1 + \dots + n \cdot M(X) \cdot M(X)^{n-1} - M(X)^n \cdot M(X^0)$

We derive $\mu_n = v_n - n \cdot v_{n-1} \cdot v_1 + \dots - n \cdot v_1 \cdot v_1^{n-1} + v_1^n$ yoki $\mu_n = v_n - n \cdot v_{n-1} \cdot v_1 + \dots + n \cdot v_1 \cdot v_1^{n-1} - v_1^n$

It follows $\mu_n = v_n - n \cdot v_{n-1} \cdot v_1 + \dots - (n - 1)v_1^n$ yoki $\mu_n = v_n - n \cdot v_{n-1} \cdot v_1 + \dots + (n - 1)v_1^n$

Now, by generalizing the final equalities, we obtain the following sums:

$$\mu_n = \sum_{k=0}^n (1)^k \cdot C_n^k \cdot v_{n-k} \cdot v_1^k$$

The final resulting equality is called the formula that relates higher-order central moments to raw moments.

The following formulas, which connect central moments with raw moments, can be used:

$$\mu_1 = 0$$

$$\mu_2 = v_2 - v_1^2$$

$$\mu_3 = v_3 - 3v_2v_1 + 2v_1^3$$

$$\mu_4 = v_4 - 4v_3v_1 + 6v_2v_1^2 - 3v_1^4$$

$$\mu_5 = v_5 - 5v_4v_1 + 10v_3v_1^2 - 10v_2v_1^3 + 4v_1^5$$

In conclusion, when relating central moments to raw moments, the sign of the final term may be subtraction or addition depending on whether nnn is an even or odd number.

Example: Find the third-order central moment of the discrete random variable given below.

X	1	3
P	0,9	0.1

Solution: First, we need the formula for the third-order central moment, that is:

$$\mu_3 = v_3 - 3v_2v_1 + 2v_1^3$$

Here, it is necessary to find the 1st, 2nd, and 3rd-order raw moments.

$$v_1 = 1 \cdot 0,9 + 3 \cdot 0,1 = 1,2 \quad ; \quad v_2 = 1^2 \cdot 0,9 + 3^2 \cdot 0,1 = 1,8 \quad ; \quad v_3 = 1^3 \cdot 0,9 + 3^3 \cdot 0,1 = 3,6$$

$$\mu_3 = v_3 - 3v_2v_1 + 2v_1^3 = 3,6 - 3 \cdot 1,8 \cdot 1,2 + 2 \cdot 1,2^3 = 0,576$$

REFERENCES:

1. S.X.Sirojiddinov, M.Mamatov: «Ehtimollar nazariyasi va matematik statistika», Toshkent, «O‘qituvchi», 1980.
2. Sh.Q.Farmonov «Ehtimollar nazariyasi», Toshkent, 2014.
3. A.Abdushukurov, T.Zuparov. «Ehtimollar nazariyasi va matematik statistika», Darslik, Tafakkur-Bo‘stoni, Toshkent, 2015.
4. V.E.Gmurman. «Ehtimollar nazariyasi va matematik statistikadan misol va masalalar yechish uchun uslubiy ko‘rsatmalar» Toshkent, 2003 y.
5. A.A.Abdushukurov, T.A.Azlarov, A.A.Djamirzayev «Ehtimollar nazariyasi va matematik statistikadan misol va masalalar to‘plami» Toshkent, «Universitet», 2003 y.
6. A.A.Abdushukurov «Ehtimollar nazariyasidan ma‘ruzalar matni», Toshkent, «O‘zMU», 2000 y.
7. V.E.Gmurman. «Ehtimollar nazariyasi va matematik statistika» Toshkent, 1987 y.